

Level and type of Educational anxiety among senior secondary school students of Kashmir valley

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Abstract: The present study was conducted to find the level of Educational anxiety among senior secondary school students. In order to obtain accurate and relevant data descriptive survey method and stratified random sampling technique was used in the present study. The sample size of the study was 202 senior secondary school students from Baramulla district of Kashmir. In order to collect data for the study scale on Educational anxiety by Vishal Sood and Arti Anand (2015) was used. The objective of the study was to analyze the level of educational anxiety and to find the differences in Educational anxiety with respect to gender and type of school. Null hypothesis were framed in order to test the objectives. Statistical techniques like mean, percentage, standard deviation and t-test were used. The results of the study revealed that maximum of the senior secondary school students are having average level of test anxiety and average level of academic anxiety. There is no significant difference between male and female senior secondary school students in their academic and educational anxiety, but there is significant difference between male and female senior secondary school students in test anxiety. Male reported high level of test anxiety as compared to female. It was also found that there is significant difference between government and private senior secondary school students in test anxiety and academic anxiety.

Keywords: Educational anxiety

INTRODUCTION

Students are considered as the backbone and priceless human resource of society. Students of the world are aggressively participating in all challenging tasks and decision making processes because it affects not only their lives but also their entire society as well. Education is the best way to cultivate the minds of the student's completely; it is the best way to achieve the desired outcomes for any society. In the present scenario educational anxiety is considered as one of the deadly and biggest emotional and psychological problem among students, Problems related to curriculum overload and examination system of school are the problems personified in educational anxiety. So there is a need to rehabilitate the students whose performance and confidence has been deterred by the educational anxiety.

Educational anxiety is an uncomfortable feeling of uneasiness or worrying about something that is happening or might happen in future. It is a situation in which we always feel worried and scared. Anxiety is a general term that causes restlessness, sacredness, horror, and nervousness. Educational anxiety leads to poor academic achievement and it also leads to poor involvement in class. Every year the school dropout increases drastically, it is only because of anxiety. Academic consequences lead to heavy economic losses for society. Anxious students understand easy situation as aggressive and dangerous. Researchers found that stress and anxiety is one of the dangerous mental problem among students predominantly in under graduate students because of extreme load of difficult courses, less time for completion of assignment and preparation for examination, students need to manage their stress for further learning. Students stress should not be ignored because it affects their health badly (University of Oregon, 2003).

(Pantic, 2010) defined Educational anxiety as an unpleasant condition of mind which is characterized by negative thinking and it leads to many negative effects such as low score in academics and less concentration (Spielberg, 1972). Educational anxiety is as an unwanted reaction towards evaluation. It is one of the dangerous problems among students throughout the world (Khosravi, 2008). Educational anxiety is a psychological condition in students. A little bit of anxiety is very helpful during exams to get motivated but so much of anxiety is not helpful to perform well in a given task (Bigdedi, 2009). Educational anxiety refers to the mental fear experienced by students when they have to face any kind of examination (Arul, 2014). Educational anxiety refers to a unique form of anxiety which is characterized by cognitive symptoms' in anxiety in condition of performing the given task.

Anxiety is sometimes also known as unfixed panic. It informs the persons of their likes, their self- responsiveness and special tasks and brings them from an inert nearness to self- conscious expression. A person becomes truthfully conscious of their impending through the familiarity of anxiety. So we can say that a little bit of anxiety is very useful in the exams to get motivated but too much of anxiety is very harmful for our health as well as our academic achievement (Eubank, 1993).

A study conducted by Singh (2015) suggested that academic achievement and moderate level of anxiety are positively correlated. He found that if there is low anxiety level the score in academic achievement is high and if the level of anxiety is high then the score in academic achievement is low. Modi (2005) found that the general caste and schedule caste had average level of general anxiety and low level of academic achievement. He also found that no significant difference between academic achievement of general and schedule caste students. Agrawal (2006) found that academic anxiety and Deprivation are positively correlated with each other. He also found that girls who are more emotionally stable are having greater academic anxiety. It is only because of lack of support and guidance from parents and other siblings. A study conducted by Soroson and Haris (2003) found that the high level of anxiety effects person's normal life. Students with high level of anxiety shows inactive attitude towards learning such as getting lower grades in exams.

Peleg (2004) found that Students who undergo from educational anxiety get lower grades in exams, approve deprived proficiency values, having sturdy breakdown evaluations, and also go down of school in total. (Jacob, 2012) conducted a study in which he found that Educational anxiety can have an effect on individual purpose and personal enjoyment as well as educational efficiency. Self-efficiency conception is considered as an imperative psychological belief for its effective role in the minds of educated people it encourage, improve their capacities, moulding the behaviour, and at last building positive attitude towards individual ability to tackle the problems.

So, to conclude we can say that educational anxiety is becoming major problem day by day so there is a need to improve the academic status of such students who are lacking in emotional stability, academic performance and systematic counselling.

Objectives of the study

The objectives formulated for the present study were:-

1. To analyze the level of educational anxiety among senior secondary school students.
2. To find the differences in educational anxiety with respect to gender and type of school.

Hypotheses

In the light of forgoing objectives following null hypothesis were framed for the present study:-

1. There exists no significant difference in educational anxiety of male and female senior secondary school students.
2. There exists no significant difference in educational anxiety of government and private senior secondary school students.

Method

The present study is descriptive in nature so descriptive survey method was used. The sample consists of 202 senior secondary school students from government and private schools affiliated to state board of school education (BOSE). The investigator used stratified random sampling in order to collect data from different senior secondary schools. For data collection Educational anxiety inventory developed by Vishal Sood and Arti Anand (2015) was used. The educational anxiety inventory comprises of 42 items out of which two items were positive. Educational anxiety inventory consists of two dimensions namely test anxiety and academic anxiety. Test anxiety comprises of 20 items and academic anxiety comprises of 22 items.

Results and Analysis

Analysis of data means studying the tabulated data in order to determine the inherent facts. It involves breaking up of complex factors into simpler parts and putting them in new arrangement for the purpose of interpretation.

The distribution of scores showing the levels of test anxiety dimension of Educational anxiety among senior secondary school students is given in table 1.1.

Table 1.1: showing the level of test anxiety among senior secondary school students

Levels	Frequency	Percent
Extremely High	3	1.5
High	14	6.9
Above average	34	16.8
Average	89	44.1
Below average	32	15.8
Low	18	8.9
Extremely Low	12	5.9
Total	202	100.0

Table 1.1 shows the seven levels of Test Anxiety namely extremely high, high, above average, average, below average, low and extremely low. It is clear from the table 3.9 that 1.5% of senior secondary school students possess extremely high level of Test Anxiety, 6.9% of senior secondary students possess high level of Test Anxiety and 16.8% of senior secondary students possess above average level of Test Anxiety. Table also revealed that 44.1% of senior secondary students are having average level of Test Anxiety, 15.8% of senior secondary students possess below average level of Test Anxiety, 8.9% of senior secondary students possess low level of Test Anxiety, and only 5.9% of senior secondary students possess extremely low level of Test Anxiety. So it can be interpreted from the table that maximum of the senior secondary students are having average level of Test Anxiety.

Table: 1.2 showing the level of Academic anxiety among senior secondary school students

Levels	Frequency	Percent
Extremely high	7	3.5
High	26	12.9
Above average	39	19.3
Average	64	31.7
Below average	38	18.8
Low	21	10.4
Extremely high	7	3.5
Total	202	100.0

Table 1.2 shows the seven levels of Academic Anxiety namely extremely high, high, above average, average, below average, low and extremely low. It is clear from the table that 3.5% of senior secondary school students possess extremely high level of Academic Anxiety, 12.9% of senior secondary students possess high level of Educational anxiety and 19.3% of senior secondary students possess above average level of Academic Anxiety. Table 1.2 further revealed that 31.7% of senior secondary students are having average level of Academic Anxiety, 18.8% of senior secondary students possess below average level of Academic Anxiety, 10.4% of senior secondary students possess low level of Academic Anxiety, and only 3.5% of senior secondary students possess extremely low level of Academic Anxiety. So it can be interpreted from the table that maximum of the senior secondary students are having average level of Academic Anxiety.

Table: 1.3 showing the levels of educational anxiety among senior secondary school students

Levels	Frequency	Percent
Extremely high	4	2.0
High	11	5.4
Above average	46	22.8
Average	77	38.1
Below Average	43	21.3
Low	16	7.9
Extremely low	5	2.5
Total	202	100.0

Table 1.3 shows the seven levels of Educational Anxiety namely extremely high, high, above average, average, below average, low and extremely low. It is clear from. Table 1.3 that 2.0% of senior secondary school students possess extremely high level of Educational Anxiety 5.4% of senior secondary students possess high level of Educational Anxiety and 22.8% of senior secondary students possess above average level of Educational Anxiety. Table further revealed that 38.1% of senior secondary students are having average level of Educational Anxiety, 21.3% of senior secondary students possess below average level of Educational Anxiety, 7.9% of senior secondary students possess low level of Educational Anxiety, and only 2.5% of senior secondary students possess extremely low level of Educational Anxiety. So it can be from the table interpreted that maximum of the senior secondary students are having average level of Educational Anxiety.

The distribution of scores for male senior secondary school students on the variable Educational anxiety is given in table 1.4.

Table 1.4: showing the levels and percentage of male senior secondary students in all dimensions of Educational anxiety

LEVELS	No. of Students	EA1	EA2	EA3
Extremely High	N	2	20	30
	%	1.98	19.8	29.74
High	N	2	26	4
	%	1.98	25.96	3.96
Above Average	N	22	18	19
	%	21.78	17.82	18.81
Average	N	48	35	48
	%	47.52	34.65	47.52
Below Average	N	10	3	0
	%	9.9	2.97	0
Low	N	9	0	0
	%	8.91	0	0
Extremely low	N	8	0	0
	%	7.92	0	0

Table 1.4 shows percentage distribution of male senior secondary school students in seven decreasing levels of Test anxiety namely extremely high, high, above average, average, below average, low and extremely low. For test anxiety results revealed that 1.98% of male senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of test anxiety, 1.98% of male senior secondary school students reported high test anxiety and 21.785 of male senior secondary school stents showed above average level of test anxiety. Table 1.4 also exposed that 47.52% of male senior secondary school reported average level of test anxiety, 9.90% of male senior secondary school students reported below average level of test anxiety, 8.91% of male senior secondary school students reported low level of educational anxiety and only 7.92% of male senior secondary school students reported extremely low level of test anxiety.

In the same way in academic anxiety 19.80% of male senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of academic anxiety, 25.74% of male senior secondary school students reported high academic anxiety and 17.82 of male senior secondary school students reported above average level of academic anxiety. Table 1.4 further showed that 34.65% of male senior secondary school reported a average level of academic anxiety 2.97% of male senior secondary school students reported below average level of academic anxiety and (0%) of male senior secondary school students reported low and extremely low level of academic anxiety.

In the same way in educational anxiety 29.74% of male senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of educational anxiety, 3.96% of male senior secondary school students reported high level of educational anxiety and 18.81% of male senior secondary school students reported above average level of educational anxiety. Table 1.4 further revealed that 47.52% of male senior secondary school reported average level of educational anxiety and none (0%) of male senior secondary school students reported below average, low and extremely low level of educational anxiety.

Table: 1.5 showing the levels and percentage of female senior secondary students in all dimensions of Educational anxiety

LEVELS	No. of Students	EA1	EA2	EA3
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Extremely High	N	1	23	2
	%	0.99	22.77	1.98
High	N	9	11	7
	%	8.91	10.89	6.93
Above Average	N	12	8	19
	%	11.88	7.92	18.81
Average	N	40	41	36
	%	39.60	40.59	35.64
Below Average	N	22	5	23
	%	21.78	4.95	22.77
Low	N	9	9	10
	%	8.91	8.91	9.90
Extremely low	N	8	4	4
	%	7.92	3.96	3.96

Table 1.5 shows percentage distribution of female senior secondary school students in seven decreasing levels of Educational anxiety namely extremely high, high, above average, average, below average, low and extremely low. For test anxiety results revealed that 0.99% of female senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of test anxiety, 8.91% of female senior secondary school students reported high test anxiety and 11.88 of female senior secondary school stents showed above average level of test anxiety. Table 1.15 also exposed that 39.60% of female senior secondary school reported average level of test anxiety, 21.78% of male senior secondary school students reported below average level of test anxiety, 8.91% of test anxiety and only 7.92% of female senior secondary school students reported extremely low level of test anxiety.

For academic anxiety results revealed that 22.77% of female senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of academic anxiety, 10.89% of female senior secondary school students reported high academic anxiety and 7.92 of female senior secondary school stents showed above average level of academic anxiety. Table 1.5 also revealed that 40.59% of male senior secondary school reported average level of academic anxiety, 4.95% of male senior secondary school students reported below average level of academic anxiety academic anxiety, 8.91% of female senior secondary school students reported low level of educational anxiety and only 3.96% of female senior secondary school students reported extremely low level of academic anxiety.

For educational anxiety results revealed that 1.98% of female senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of educational anxiety, 6.93% of female senior secondary school students reported high educational anxiety and 18.81% of female senior secondary school stents showed above average level of educational anxiety. The table also revealed that 35.64% of male senior secondary school reported average level of educational anxiety, 22.77% of male senior secondary school students reported below average level of educational anxiety, 9.90% of female senior secondary school students reported low level of educational anxiety and only 3.96% of female senior secondary school students reported extremely low level of educational anxiety.

Table 1.6: showing the levels and percentage of government senior secondary students in all dimensions of Educational anxiety

LEVELS	No. of Students	EA1	EA2	EA3
Extremely High	N	3	6	4

	%	2.97	5.94	3.96
High	N	11	18	9
	%	10.89	17.82	8.91
Above Average	N	22	21	29
	%	21.78	20.79	28.71
Average	N	48	41	44
	%	47.52	40.59	43.56
Below average	N	13	10	14
	%	12.87	9.90	13.86
Low	N	4	4	1
	%	3.96	3.96	0.99
Extremely low	N	0	1	0
	%	0	0.99	0

Table 1.6 shows percentage distribution of government senior secondary school students in seven decreasing levels of Educational anxiety namely extremely high, high, above average, average, below average, low and extremely low. For test anxiety results revealed that 2.97% of government senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of test anxiety, 10.89% of female senior secondary school students reported high test anxiety and 21.78% of government senior secondary school students showed above average level of test anxiety. Table 1.6 also exposed that 47.52% of government senior secondary school reported average level of test anxiety, 12.87% of government senior secondary school students reported below average level of test anxiety, 3.96% of government senior secondary school students reported low level of test anxiety, and none of the (0%) of government senior secondary school students reported extremely low level of test anxiety.

Likewise in academic anxiety results revealed that 5.94% of government senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of academic anxiety, 17.82% of government senior secondary school students reported high academic anxiety and 20.79 of government senior secondary school students showed above average level of academic anxiety. Table 1.6 also exposed that 40.59% of government senior secondary school reported average level of academic anxiety, 9.90% of government senior secondary school students reported below average level of academic anxiety, 3.96%, of government senior secondary school students reported low level of academic anxiety, 0.99% of government senior secondary school students reported extremely low level of academic anxiety.

Similarly in Educational anxiety results revealed that 3.96% of government senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of Educational anxiety, 8.91% of government senior secondary school students reported high Educational anxiety and 28.71% of government senior secondary school students showed above average level of Educational anxiety. Table 1.6 also revealed that 43.56% of government senior secondary school reported average level of Educational anxiety, 13.86% of government senior secondary school students reported below average level of Educational anxiety, 0.99% of government senior secondary school students reported low level of Educational anxiety, and none of the (0%) of government senior secondary school students reported extremely low level of Educational anxiety.

Table 1.7 showing the levels and percentage of Private senior secondary students in all dimensions of Educational anxiety

LEVELS	No. of Students	EA1	EA2	EA3
Extremely High	N	2	2	1

	%	1.98	1.98	0.99
High	N	3	8	2
	%	2.97	7.92	1.98
Above Average	N	12	18	17
	%	11.88	17.82	16.83
Average	N	40	23	33
	%	39.60	22.77	32.67
Below average	N	17	28	28
	%	16.83	27.72	27.72
Low	N	15	16	15
	%	14.85	15.85	14.85
Extremely low	N	12	6	5
	%	11.88	5.94	4.95

Table 1.7 shows percentage distribution of private senior secondary school students in seven decreasing levels of Educational anxiety namely extremely high, high, above average, average, below average, low and extremely low. For test anxiety results revealed that 1.98% of private senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of test anxiety, 2.97% of private senior secondary school students reported high test anxiety and 11.88 of private senior secondary school stents showed above average level of test anxiety. Table 1.7 also exposed that 39.60% of private senior secondary school reported average level of test anxiety, 16.83% of private senior secondary school students reported below average level of test anxiety, 14.85%, of private senior secondary school students reported low level of test anxiety, 11.88% Of private senior secondary school students reported extremely low level of test anxiety.

For academic anxiety results revealed that 1.98% of private senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of academic anxiety, 7.92% of private senior secondary school students reported high academic anxiety and 17.82 of private senior secondary school stents showed above average level of academic anxiety. Table 1.7 also exposed that 22.77% of private senior secondary school reported average level of academic anxiety, 27.72% of private senior secondary school students reported below average level of academic anxiety, 15.85%, of private senior secondary school students reported low level of academic anxiety and 5.94% of private senior secondary school students reported extremely low level of academic anxiety.

Similarly in Educational anxiety results revealed that 0.99% of private senior secondary school students reported extremely high level of Educational anxiety, 1.98% of private senior secondary school students reported high Educational anxiety and 16.83 of private senior secondary school stents showed above average level of Educational anxiety. Table 1.7 also exposed that 32.67% of private senior secondary school reported average level of Educational anxiety, 27.72% of private senior secondary school students reported below average level of Educational anxiety, 14.85%, of private senior secondary school students reported low level of Educational anxiety and 4.95% of private senior secondary school students reported extremely low level of Educational anxiety.

Results pertaining to the differences in male and female senior secondary school students in their self-understanding dimension of Emotional self- efficacy is given in table 1.8.

Table 1.8: showing the difference between male and female students in Test anxiety

EA1	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
	Male	101	61.02	13.75	200	2.11**	.036
	Female	101	56.72	15.07			

Not significant at 0.05

It is clear from the table 1.8 that the mean score of male and female students 61.02 and 56.72 respectively. The SD for male and female students is 13.75 and 15.07 the t- value is 2.11 which is significant at 0.05 levels ($p < 0.05$). So the null hypothesis stated that there exists no significant difference between male and female senior secondary school student in their test anxiety is not accepted. So it can be interpreted that there is significant difference between male and female senior secondary school students in their test anxiety.

Further, it is obvious from the table 1.8 that mean score of female (15.07) senior secondary school students is greater than the mean score of male (13.75) senior secondary school students. So it can be interpreted that female students greater are having high test anxiety as compared to male students.

Table 1.9: showing the difference of male and female students in their Academic anxiety

EA2	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
	Male	101	64.70	14.48	200	1.290	0.199
	Female	101	61.92	16.13			

It is clear from the table 1.8 that the mean score of male and female students is 64.70 and 61.92 respectively. The SD for male and female students is 14.48 and 16.13 the t- value is 1.29 which is not significant at 0.05 levels ($p > 0.05$). So the null hypothesis stated that there exists no significant difference between male and female senior secondary school student in their academic anxiety is not accepted. So it can be interpreted that there is no significant difference between male and female senior secondary school students in their academic anxiety.

Further, it is obvious from the table 1.9 that mean score of male (64.70) senior secondary school students is greater than the mean score of female (61.92) senior secondary school students. So it can be interpreted that male students are having high academic anxiety as compared to female students. But the average difference is not too significant.

Table: 1.10: showing the difference of male and female students in Educational anxiety

EAT	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
	Male	101	125.54	25.10	200	1.799	0.074
	Female	101	118.66	29.11			

It is clear from the table 1.10 that the mean score of male and female students is 125.54 and 118.66, respectively. The SD for male and female students is 25.10 and 29.11 the t- value is 1.79 which is not significant at 0.05 levels ($p > 0.05$). So the null hypothesis stated that there exists no significant difference between male and female senior secondary school student in their Educational anxiety is accepted. So it can be interpreted that there is no significant difference between male and female senior secondary school students in their Educational anxiety.

Table 1.11: showing the difference of government and private students in their Test anxiety

EA1	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
	Government	102	64.16	11.31	200	5.59**	.000
	Private	100	53.48	15.53			

Significant at 0.01**

It is clear from the table 1.11 that the mean score of government and private students is 64.16 and 53.48 respectively. The SD for government and private students is 11.31 and 15.53 the t- value is 5.59 which is significant at 0.01 levels ($p < 0.05$) So the null hypothesis stated that there exists no significant difference between private and government senior secondary school student in their test anxiety is not accepted. So it can be interpreted that there is significant difference between government and private senior secondary school students in their test anxiety

Further, it is obvious from the table 1.11 that the mean score of government (64.16) senior secondary school student is greater than the mean score of private (53.48) senior secondary school students. So it can be interpreted that government senior secondary school students are having high test anxiety as compared to private senior secondary school students.

Table 1.12: showing the difference of govt and private students in their academic anxiety

EA2	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
	Government	102	68.42	13.94	200	5.06**	.000
	Private	100	58.10	15.03			

Significant at 0.01**

It is clear from the table 1.12 that the mean score of government and private students is 68.42 and 58.10 respectively. The SD for government and private students is 13.94 and 15.03 the t- value is 5.06 which is significant at 0.01 levels ($p < 0.05$). So the null hypothesis stated that there exists no significant difference between private and government senior secondary school student in their academic anxiety is not accepted. So it can be interpreted that there is significant difference between government and private senior secondary school students in their academic anxiety.

Further, it is obvious from the table 1.12 that the mean score of government (68.42) senior secondary school student is greater than the mean score of private (58.10) senior secondary school students. So it can be interpreted that government senior secondary school students are having high academic anxiety as compared to private senior secondary school students.

Table 1.13: showing the difference of govt and private students in their Educational anxiety

EAT	Gender	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value
	Government	102	132.61	22.79	200	5.97**	.000
	Private	100	111.39	27.51			

Significant at 0.01**

It is clear from the table 1.13 that the mean score of government and private students is 132.61 and 111.39 respectively. The SD for government and private students is 22.79 and 27.51 the t- value is 5.97 which is significant at 0.01 levels ($p < 0.05$). So the null hypothesis stated that there exists no significant difference between private and government senior secondary school student in their Educational anxiety not accepted. So it can be interpreted that there is significant difference between government and private senior secondary school students in their Educational anxiety.

Further, it is obvious from the table 1.13 that the mean score of government (132.61) senior secondary school student is greater than the mean score of private (111.39) senior secondary school students. So it can be interpreted that government senior secondary school students are having high Educational anxiety as compared to private senior secondary school students.

CONCLUSION

- Maximum of the senior secondary school students are having average or above average level of educational anxiety Majority of male and female senior secondary school reported average level of educational anxiety. Similarly in government and private senior secondary school students, government senior secondary students are having average level of educational anxiety while private senior secondary school students reported below average level to average level of educational anxiety.
- Maximum of senior secondary school students are having average level of test anxiety. Majority of male, female, government and private senior secondary school reported average level of test anxiety.
- Maximum of senior secondary school students are having average or above average level of academic anxiety. Majority of male senior secondary school students reported average level of academic anxiety at the same time female senior secondary school students also reported average level of academic anxiety. Similarly in government and private senior secondary school students, government senior secondary school students reported average level of academic anxiety while as private senior secondary school students reported below average to average level of academic anxiety.
- Male and Female senior secondary school students do not differ significantly in their test anxiety. Male students showed high level of test anxiety as compared to female students. But in academic anxiety and educational anxiety no significant difference was found between male and female senior secondary school students.
- Government and private senior secondary school students differ significantly in their test anxiety, academic anxiety and educational anxiety. Government senior secondary school students reported high anxiety as compared to private senior secondary school.

Recommendations

- As maximum number of senior secondary school students showed some level of Educational anxiety so it is recommended to students that when they enter into new institutions or take admissions in new colleges, they should take proper guidance from counselling cell to know about their capability for accepting new challenges.
- As male students have higher test anxiety as compared to female, counselling sessions and activities should be organized for them by schools. Parents should also not have very high expectations from them. Further as male students perceive lower peer support which can be the reason of higher test anxiety, measures should be taken to increase group learning and peer support.
- As government senior secondary school students have high level of educational anxiety and compared to private school students, the counselling sessions, yoga, meditations, drill and practice of content should be increased in government schools.

References

- Alam, M. (2001). Academic Achievement in Relation to Socio Economic Status, Anxiety Level and Achievement Motivation: A Comparative Study of Muslim and Non-Muslim School Children of Uttar Pradesh. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(2), 57-65.
- Banga, C. L. (2015). A Study of Academic Anxiety among Private Senior Secondary School Students of Kangra District. *International General of English, Literature and Humanities (IJELH)* Volume, 3.
- Syokwaa, K. A., Aloka, P. J., & Ndunge, S. N. F. (2014). The Relationship between Anxiety Levels and Academic Achievement among Students in Selected Secondary Schools in Lang'ata District, Kenya. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 4(3), 403.
- Bihari, S. (2014). Academic Anxiety among Secondary School Students with reference to Gender, Habitat and Types of School. *International Journal of Education and Psychological Research (IJEPR)* Volume, 3.
- Deb, S., Chatterjee, P., & Walsh, K. (2010). Anxiety among High School Students in India: Comparisons across Gender, School Type, Social Strata and Perceptions of Quality Time with Parents. *Australian Journal of Educational & Developmental Psychology*, 10, 18-31.

Erozkan, A. (2012). Examination of Relationship between Anxiety Sensitivity and Parenting Styles in Adolescents. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 12(1), 52-57.

Nadeem, M., Ali, A., Maqbool, S., & Zaidi, S. U. (2012). Impact of Anxiety on The Academic Achievement of Students Having Different Mental Abilities at University Level in Bahawalpur (Southern Punjab) Pakistan. *International Online Journal of Educational Sciences*, 4(3), 519-528.

Rezazadeh, M., & Tavakoli, M. (2009). Investigating the Relationship Among Test Anxiety, Gender, Academic Achievement and Years of Study: A Case of Iranian EFL University Students. *English Language Teaching*, 2(4), 68.

Sindhu, P. (2016). Impact of Anxiety on Academic Achievement among Engineering Students . *International Journal of Basic Sciences & Applied Research*, 3, 261-5.

Vitasari, P., Wahab, M. N. A., Othman, A., & Awang, M. G. (2010). A Research for Identifying Study Anxiety Sources Among University Students. *International Education Studies*, 3(2), 189.

Websites

www.ijhssnet.com.

www.newcastle.edu.au